

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN STAFFING THE ACTIVITIES OF INVESTIGATIVE UNITS

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Annotation. This article analyzes the theoretical-legal and organizational-practical foundations of staffing investigative units within internal affairs bodies from a comparative legal perspective, drawing on foreign experience. The mechanisms for the selection, training, evaluation, and accreditation of investigative personnel in the United Kingdom, Germany, Japan, Singapore, Canada, and other countries are examined; the significance of meritocracy, competency-based assessment, portfolio and workplace assessment, leadership training, as well as the integrity infrastructure is scientifically substantiated. In addition, the impact of a human resource management (HRM) system integrated with principles of human rights and accountability on the quality of investigative activities is explored. Based on the findings of the study, scientific and practical recommendations have been developed to improve the system of staffing investigative units in the context of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: investigative units, staffing (personnel provision), personnel policy, theoretical and legal foundations, civil service, meritocracy, procedural independence, human resource capacity (personnel potential), competency model, rational bureaucracy, staff stability, professionalism.

The relevance of the topic and its significance today lies in the fact that the investigative units under the internal affairs departments are the decisive link ensuring the quality of criminal proceedings.

Although the procedure and powers of proceedings are defined in criminal procedure legislation, in practice, the quality of the investigation largely depends on the level of functioning of the personnel selection, training, mentoring (the process of guiding a less experienced person (mentor) in professional, personal, or scientific development), workload, internal control, and integrity systems.

In recent years, "targeted work," prevention, and interdepartmental cooperation in public administration and ensuring public safety have been strengthened; The fact that Resolution No. PP-1 of January 5, 2026, emphasizes an integrated system and targeted measures to ensure a safe environment in mahallas also increases the information-analytical and procedural burden on investigative bodies. This places the management of personnel quality in investigative units as a separate institutional task.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev established a comprehensive system for training personnel for investigations - the Law Enforcement Academy. More than 200 investigators are trained there annually. But in the capital, 100 investigator positions in internal affairs have been vacant for three months. It was noted that the quality is declining due to the fact that this burden also falls on other employees. The acquittal of 422 persons in court

in 2025 indicates that judges make independent decisions. This is, of course, good! But there is another side to the matter. Who will be responsible for the fact that so many people were illegally accused? In the investigation, there should be quality, not quantity.

Therefore, it is necessary to improve the activities of investigative bodies based on advanced foreign experience, and it is very important that investigators in internal affairs perform their official duties independently of the heads of territorial internal affairs bodies in order to avoid conflicts of interest. [1]

Responsible officials were instructed to review the activities of investigative bodies and staffing levels in accordance with the scope of work, and to submit a package of resolutions and draft laws.

Since investigative activity requires a high level of legal knowledge, analytical thinking, a culture of working with evidence, procedural independence, and strict adherence to professional ethics, the personnel selection-training-evaluation system must be scientifically based and institutionally stable. From this point of view, the experience of developed countries shows that it has served to improve the quality of investigations through the introduction of a competency-based approach in personnel policy, phased qualification standards, mechanisms for professional accreditation and continuous retraining.

In this article, these experiences are analyzed in comparative-legal and organizational-practical approaches, and scientific conclusions on improving the mechanisms for staffing investigative units are substantiated. This article consists of a comparative analysis of the experience of Great Britain, the USA, Germany, Japan, Singapore, and Canada, the conceptualization of their advanced solutions in the context of investigative units, and the substantiation of transformation directions appropriate to the conditions of Uzbekistan. From the point of view of international standards, a system of successful personnel management (HRM) and ethical culture, based on value and dignity, plays a key role in strengthening public trust in public service.

According to Herbert Simon, the quality of decision-making in government bodies directly depends on the knowledge and intellectual potential of employees. Therefore, the introduction of multi-stage examinations (assessment of theoretical knowledge, practical skills, and analytical thinking) during admission to investigative bodies will improve the quality of decisions. [3]

In this article, the work of foreign countries in this area was mainly analyzed as follows.

- normative legal acts and official materials;
- departmental standards and educational regulations;

In Great Britain, the training and evaluation of investigative personnel are regulated by national standards through the "Professionalising Investigations Programme (PIP)." PIP was introduced in 2003, and its main idea is to ensure the gradual development of investigative skills through national comparison with the chain of training-examination-work and on-site assessment-accreditation.

Professionalising Investigations Programme (PIP) is a comprehensive system of the UK government aimed at professionalizing, standardizing, and improving the quality of investigative activities.

The legal and organizational significance of PIP lies in the fact that the investigator's training is not limited to "participation in the course"; the required result is to prove

operational competence through a reliable "portfolio" in practice[4]. Portfolio (documents, a collection of works that show the work, results and achievements that a person (or organization) can do) - usually includes such indicators as the formalization of case materials, the basis of decisions, work with evidence, cooperation with other departments, work with victims and witnesses, compliance with moral and legal guarantees.

PIP levels are systematized as follows:

- PIP Level 1 is the initial stage, the level of investigation of crimes of a simple type, for example, theft, hooliganism, minor robbery, traffic accidents, and small-scale fraud. At this investigative level, the investigator, in the process of work, improves their experience mainly in the following aspects (collection and formalization of evidence, proper communication with the victim and witnesses, proper maintenance of procedural documents, observance of investigative ethics and human rights).

This level of investigation serves as the foundation of the investigator's profession. At this stage, the investigator, along with complying with established requirements (standards), forms their basic professional qualifications.

- PIP Level 2 is a specialized (for crimes of high social danger and complexity) level of investigation. This involves investigating complex crimes (intentional infliction of grievous bodily harm, sexual offenses, large-scale fraud, multi-episode criminal cases). At this level of investigation, the given investigative staff develops the following competencies (knowledge, skills, qualifications, experience, and personal qualities), that is, the ability to plan the investigation and develop versions, work with expert opinions, protect victims (victim-centered approach), and analyze complex evidence. An investigator at the PIP2 level develops as a specialist, and making mistakes at this level directly affects court decisions.

PIP Level 3 - high level (investigation of especially serious crimes). Conducting investigations of especially serious and high-profile crimes (murder, terrorism, organized crime, cases of mass media coverage). The investigative personnel assigned this investigative level develops the following competencies: managing large investigative teams, making strategic decisions, risk management, and high-level cooperation with the prosecutor's office and the court. PIP 3 is considered an elite investigative level. At this stage, along with personal competence, leadership and strategic thinking are of decisive importance.

PIP Level 4 - Strategic leadership, the level of systemic and strategic management of investigative activities, in which complex work at the national level, the definition of investigative policy and standards, the coordination of large resources, this level of investigation develops the following competencies of the given investigative personnel, i.e., strategic management and decision-making, assessment of institutional risks, control over the quality of investigations, personnel policy and training in the specified areas. The PIP 4 level employee is not the investigator, but the architect (organizer) of the investigative system. He is responsible for the effectiveness of the entire system.

Peter Drucker emphasizes the importance of a system of selection and evaluation in the effective management of human capital. In his opinion, the exam in investigative bodies should be not only a means of checking knowledge, but also an instrument for determining the professional potential and developmental abilities of an employee. [5]

German experience: The criminal police system in Germany is organized at the federal and territorial (Land) levels. The Federal Criminal Police Office - Bundeskriminalamt (BKA)

participates in the training and advanced training of investigative personnel within its competence. On the official page of the Federal Criminal Police Office, it is reported that he trains employees of the CID Criminal Investigation Department, which specializes in investigating crimes within his police system, and that candidates for officers receive training through three years of study at the Federal College[6].

In the German model, the professional experience of an investigator relies on the complexity of "legal thinking, criminalistics, management." Theoretical training is carried out in conjunction with practice, which contributes to the reliability of evidence, the standardization of documentation, and the stability of procedural decisions. From a comparative point of view, such a model is explained by increasing the probability of accepting evidence in court and a stable outcome of the case.

Agencies at the federal level also influence agencies at the regional level through investigative methodology and special courses. As a result, national methodological standards are formed: working with evidence, using forensic laboratories, ensuring the safety of the scene, storing and sending digital evidence.

Japanese experience: In Japan, the central coordinating body in the police system is the National Police Agency (NPA), and the National Police Academy (affiliated with the NPA) plays a special role in the training of investigative and managerial personnel. According to official information, the National Police Academy conducts high-level training and preparation courses for employees who are expected to be appointed to leadership positions, the goal of which is the development of managerial and leadership skills, as well as practical skills[7].

A distinctive feature of the Japanese model is the centralized training of the upper part of the personnel pyramid (inspectors, department heads, management personnel). This procedure ensures the preservation of institutional memory, interdepartmental coordination, and uniformity of standards. Comparative studies also analyzed the personnel composition in Japanese police education, the purpose of education, and the system of police schools[8].

The Japanese police have also instituted training on international cooperation in the context of transnational threats. This, in turn, develops language, international legal assistance (MLA), extradition, joint operations, and information exchange competencies in investigative personnel.

Ernest van den Haag argues that if strict examination requirements are not implemented in the criminal justice system, the professional level will decline. In his opinion, the selection of investigators requires comprehensive examinations covering legal knowledge, moral stability, and stress resistance[9].

Singapore experience: Singapore Police Force (National Police Service of Singapore: a single national police body engaged in maintaining public order, preventing and investigating crimes, ensuring public safety) uses the resident (campus-based learning) model in training officers. According to official information, the service for the Direct Entry Inspector (which means a path to recruitment for the police service "without starting from a regular position," directly "Inspector" (inspector) depending on the officer's rank, position rank) begins with a 9-month resident training program; it includes police defense tactics, physical training, criminal law, leadership development, as well as criminal investigation lessons and additional leadership training (with a foreign segment) [10].

In the Singaporean model, the officer's influence combines "team management, operational decision-making, investigation standards." From the point of view of investigative units, this is especially important in the distribution of work, procedural discipline, responsibility for results, and professional development of personnel. In other words, personnel training simultaneously forms the competence of "activity management."

Canadian experience: in Canada, basic training through the RCMP (National Academy of Personnel Training) Academy (Deputy Division) was organized as a Cadet Training Program (this is the main basic training course conducted at the RCMP Academy (Deputy Division) for newly admitted personnel (cadets) to the Royal Canadian Mounted Police (RCMP). According to the official RCMP (National Academy of Personnel Training), this program is a 26-week comprehensive basic training, offered in two official languages; successfully graduating cadets can be offered service in the National (Federal) Police Service of Canada, and they will have the status of a peace officer with the authority to maintain public order [11].

According to a report by the Government of Canada's Management Advisory Board, the 26-week training course is described as a fundamental program for the National Academy of Personnel Training and provides recommendations for its improvement in accordance with the goals of creating a future-oriented, inclusive, and healthy organization[12]. An important trend here is that personnel training is associated not only with professional skills, but also with service culture, stress management, psychological stability, and ethics. In investigative units, these factors (burnout, emotional pressure) can influence the risks of wrong decisions.

A.Kh. Saidov emphasizes that the introduction of an examination system for admission to law enforcement agencies in the conditions of Uzbekistan is an institutional guarantee of legality and the protection of human rights. In his opinion, it is possible to ensure the principle of meritocracy in investigative bodies through transparent examinations. [13]

Comparative analysis shows that in developed countries, investigative personnel policy is not limited to training; it is based on merit HRM (Human Resource Management) - a system of human resource management, i.e., the selection, development, and effective management of personnel in an organization, institutionally linked to integrity infrastructure and human rights standards. In its practical guide, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) emphasizes that a merit-based system in public service strengthens public integrity through transparency and objectivity [14].

The UN Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) Handbook states that police accountability should be ensured through a system of internal and external controls, balances and constraints, and that police discipline and anti-corruption mechanisms should be assessed.[15] The OSCE's practical guide to action on security, human rights, democracy and the rule of law identifies the rule of law, police ethics, human rights, and public accountability as the main goals of democratic police[16].

The UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) Handbook for Law Enforcement offers training in a methodical format, based on model goals, training plans, question-and-answer sessions, and case studies for trainers.[17] These standards serve to form a practice in the preparation of investigations free from coercion, based on evidence and legal guarantees.

When summarizing and analyzing the experience of developed countries, the following conclusions are drawn:

Firstly, transparent and strict selection mechanisms (requirements, tests, security checks, competency assessment) are central to personnel selection.

Secondly, the training programs require theoretical knowledge and practical training, skills in simulation, scenario cases, gathering and documenting evidence, and question-and-answer sessions.

Thirdly, assessment and accreditation at the workplace have become the main means of checking the real competence of personnel.

Fourthly, leadership training, especially for high-ranking officials, is the ability to make decisive decisions in effectively managing complex tasks.

Fifthly, principles and human rights standards are considered as an integral part of preparation.

Summarizing the above experience, the following scientific and practical proposals are considered justified for investigative units under the internal affairs bodies of Uzbekistan:

- 1) for investigators within the framework of national competence (levels: I-IV) implementation;
- 2) institutionalization of the criteria of merit (the principle that a person achieves a position, reward, or opportunity based on knowledge, skills, and results, and not on acquaintances or personal connections) and integrity (the ability to act without conflict of interest, while remaining faithful to the law, ethics, and professional norms) in admission;
- 3) Simulation in training and establishing a system for evaluating documents, work samples (portfolio), confirming the knowledge, skills, achievements, and experience of a person from the workplace;
- 4) organization of special courses (major case management) for high-ranking managers on special leadership and systematically coordinated management of serious and especially serious criminal cases (murder, terrorism, human trafficking, organized crime);
- 5) transfer of the specialist's knowledge, skills, and competencies to the system of regular updating and improvement during work activities (CPD) and linking them to work results;
- 6) standardization of special competencies in digital evidence (digital forensics, a method of correct and safe data management).

Similar to the PIP investigative levels in Britain, it is necessary to divide national-level investigative work into competency levels from simple to complex, clearly defining the knowledge and skills required for each level.

Within this level, the following areas are performed as a robust, legitimate, and well-founded module:

- making a procedural decision;
- chain of evidence, i.e., complete documentation of the actions of the material evidence from the moment of its discovery until its submission to the court (chain of custody);
- investigative actions;
- work with forensics and expertise;
- digital evidence;
- the issue of procedural measures and human rights;
- preparation of the case for trial;
- interdepartmental cooperation processes.

Accreditation is carried out through a person's work experience and workplace assessment, which becomes the main criterion for promotion and placement in responsible positions.

In accordance with the recommendations of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), ensuring transparency and objectivity based on merit (assessment of a person based on their performance and knowledge) in public service strengthens the culture of integrity (the ability to act in accordance with the law, ethics, and professional standards, without conflict of interest).

In the activities of investigative units, this is ensured by:

- disclosure of admission and appointment criteria;
- standardization of exams and questions and answers;
- identification and documentation of conflicts of interest;
- interaction with internal control bodies;
- verification of the degree of compliance with the established law and regulations;
- such as ethics training during service.

The UN Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC) Handbook emphasizes the importance of internal and external anti-corruption controls, complaints mechanisms, and disciplinary rules [15].

Sh.R. Kushbakov cites the practice of hiring personnel without sufficient knowledge and skills as one of the reasons for procedural errors in investigative activities. In his opinion, to solve this problem, it is necessary to introduce a system of mandatory professional examinations and certification. [18]

Human Rights Standards: The UN Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) provides a methodology for organizing training in accordance with the human rights standard [17].

In the preparation of the investigative process, this serves the following tasks:

- prevention of coercion and unlawful influence;
- protection of victims and witnesses;
- explanation and ensuring of procedural rights;
- proportionality in investigative actions such as detention, search, seizure (when applying restrictions or procedural enforcement measures, it should correspond to the severity of the situation);
- compliance with standards affecting the admissibility of evidence in court cases.

A practical guide from the International Regional Organization for Security, Human Rights, Democracy and the Rule of Law (OSCE) also emphasizes the need to consider human rights and public accountability as a system in police ethics.

[see 16].

Based on the results of the analysis of the above data, the following conclusions are drawn:

- in developed countries, the training of investigative personnel is standardized through national standards or central academies;
- competency-based assessment (portfolio, workplace assessment, accreditation) improves the quality of investigation and accountability;
- leadership training (especially for senior officials) is an important factor in the effectiveness of the investigation;

- Merit-based HRM (Human Resource Management) is human resource management, i.e., a system for selecting, developing, and effectively managing employees in an organization and integrity infrastructure, which reduces the risk of corruption in personnel policy and strengthens public trust[19];

- training in accordance with human rights serves to ensure legal guarantees and procedural legality in investigative practice[20].

The results of this study show that the issue of staffing investigative units is not only an organizational and staffing problem, but also a strategic institutional factor that determines the effectiveness of the rule of law and the justice system. Based on a comparative analysis, it was established that in developed countries, the policy of investigative personnel is carried out in close connection with mechanisms of competence-based selection, phased professional development, accreditation, and assessment at the workplace.

Foreign experience confirms that the HRM system, based on the principles of meritocracy and integrity, is the main condition for ensuring procedural independence, accountability, and quality standards in investigative activities. A comprehensive approach to the training of investigators, combining theoretical knowledge, practical skills, analytical thinking, and professional ethics, ensures the admissibility of evidence and the stability of decisions in court. At the same time, it has been scientifically substantiated that leadership training and strategic management skills are of decisive importance for personnel in senior positions.

The research results indicate the need to institutionalize the national competency model, staged qualification levels, a transparent examination and accreditation system, continuous professional development (CPD), and training in accordance with human rights standards in the personnel policy of investigative units in the conditions of Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, ensuring the principle of "quality, not quantity" in investigative activities can be achieved through the introduction of scientifically based, transparent, and sustainable mechanisms for the selection, training, and evaluation of personnel. This will serve to strengthen legality in criminal proceedings, reliably protect the rights and freedoms of citizens, and increase public trust.

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